

Teachers' Classroom Mentoring Attitude and Intellectual Satisfaction of Students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

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Abstract. The study aimed to look into the influence of teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes on the intellectual satisfaction of students. In this study, the researcher selected 160 elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, as the respondents of the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes and intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte were rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes and the intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. Evidently, regression analysis proved that teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of administering discipline and academic consultation were significant predictors of students' intellectual satisfaction. It was recommended that students should advocate for supportive learning environments where their intellectual needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are met.

KEY WORDS

1. educational management
2. teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes
3. intellectual satisfaction of students

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1. Introduction

Teachers' classroom mentoring attitude and students' intellectual satisfaction are critically important factors in the educational process, as they influence various aspects of teaching and learning. A positive classroom mentoring attitude fosters a supportive and encouraging learning environment, which can lead to increased student engagement. Engaged students are more motivated to participate actively in their education. Also, intellectual satisfaction often correlates with improved learning outcomes. Students are more likely to comprehend and retain information when intellectually satisfied, leading to better academic performance. Furthermore, classroom mentoring attitudes encouraging curiosity and inquisitiveness can spark students' interest in the subject. This curiosity fuels a natural desire to learn and explore beyond the required curriculum. Hence, teachers' classroom mentoring attitude and students' intellectual satisfaction play pivotal roles in the educational process. They contribute to a positive learning environment, improved learning outcomes, and the development of motivated,

engaged, and self-directed learners. However, Asakereh and Dehghannezhad (2015) reported that students who do not experience intellectual satisfaction may lack motivation to engage in their studies. They may view learning as a chore rather than a source of personal fulfillment. Accordingly, lack of intellectual satisfaction can lead to decreased academic performance. Students may struggle to concentrate, retain information, or complete assignments, resulting in lower grades. Similarly, Romero-Frías and Arquero (2013) reported that students who are not intellectually satisfied are more likely to be disengaged in the classroom. They may exhibit passive learning behaviors, such as daydreaming or distraction, which hinder their overall learning experience. More so, Teeroovengadam et al. (2016) indicated that a lack of intellectual satisfaction can lead to reduced interest in learning. Students may become disinterested in exploring new topics or pursuing academic challenges. As Mayo (2016) pointed out, intellectual satisfaction is the sense of contentment, fulfillment, and gratification that students experience in their intellectual pursuits and educational endeavors. According to Mandera (2013), intellectual satisfaction is a powerful intrinsic motivator. Students who find their studies intellectually satisfying are more likely to be self-motivated learners, taking the initiative to explore topics beyond the curriculum and set higher academic goals. More so, Vidić (2021) showed that intellectual satisfaction is closely linked to critical thinking skills. Satisfied students are more inclined to think critically, analyze information, and apply their knowledge to solve complex problems, which are essential skills for success in various fields. According to Pesigan (2019), a classroom where students experience intellectual satisfaction tends to have a positive and vibrant climate. Meanwhile, Lai-Yeung (2014) viewed that classroom mentoring attitude is the disposition, mindset, and approach that educators adopt when providing guidance, support, and mentorship to their students within the classroom setting. More so, Ahmad and Zadha (2018) noted that teachers who possess a mentoring attitude are more likely to provide academic guidance, individualized instruction, and opportunities for students to seek help when facing challenges. This support can significantly improve students' academic performance and confidence. According to Thankur (2019), teachers with strong mentoring attitudes are more likely to actively engage with their students, both academically and personally. This engagement can lead to increased student participation and enthusiasm in classroom activities. As noted by Scribner (2019), teachers who display curiosity and enthusiasm for the subject matter can inspire students to become more intellectually curious themselves. When teachers approach teaching with passion and a love for learning, students are more likely to adopt a similar attitude. Adding more, Page and Kulick (2016) found that teachers who offer constructive and encouraging feedback help students see setbacks and mistakes as opportunities for growth rather than failures. This can boost students' confidence and motivation to learn. More so, Kangas et al. (2017) concluded that teachers who acknowledge and celebrate students' achievements, no matter how small, can boost students' self-esteem and motivation. This recognition reinforces a sense of intellectual satisfaction and accomplishment. While there is existing research indicating a positive correlation between teachers' mentoring attitudes and student satisfaction, there is limited research that delves into the specific factors or processes through which mentoring attitudes influence intellectual satisfaction. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for developing more targeted and effective strategies to enhance students' intellectual satisfaction in the classroom. Thus, it is on this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine set-

ting, particularly in Dujali District in Davao del Norte using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher made used descriptive correlational design through regression analysis to

understand the intellectual satisfaction of students as determined by the teachers' classroom mentoring attitude, which is found to be scarce.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized the quantitative descriptive-correlational technique of research to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the influence of teachers' classroom mentoring attitude on the intellectual satisfaction of students. Bryman and Bell (2015) described quantitative research as a research method that focuses on the objective measurement and analysis of numerical data to draw conclusions and make inferences about a specific population or phenomenon. This approach employs systematic and structured data collection techniques, such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis of existing datasets, to gather numerical data that could be quantified and statistically analyzed. The findings from quantitative research aim to provide a deeper understanding of patterns, relationships, and trends within the data. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Gay, Mills, and Airasian (2019), was an approach that involves observing and measuring two or more variables without manipulating them. It aims to describe the relationship or association between variables as they naturally occur. This approach focuses on understanding the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, often using statistical measures such as correlation coefficients. In a descriptive correlational study, researchers collect data on variables of interest and analyze them to identify patterns, trends, or associations. The goal is to gain a deeper understanding of how the variables relate to each

other in a specific population or context. More so, this approach is particularly useful when exploring complex phenomena or when causality cannot be established due to ethical or practical limitations. Particularly, the study focused on determining which domains of teachers' classroom mentoring attitude significantly influence the intellectual satisfaction of students.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. In this study, the 160 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular teachers in Dujali District in Davao del Norte who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions, and thus, it did not consider the performance rating of the teachers.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study used adapted and modified survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. The scaling was done by using one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Also, the survey ques-

tionnaires underwent validation by an external and internal panel of experts. The first tool is about teachers' classroom mentoring attitude. This questionnaire was adapted from Lai-Yeung (2014), which has four indicators, namely: emotional support, administering discipline, parents' coordination, and academic consultation. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach's alpha value of 0.945 interpreted as excellent, in-

dicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers' classroom mentoring attitude, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean Descriptive Levels and Interpretations

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers' classroom mentoring attitude is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The teachers' classroom mentoring attitude is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers' classroom mentoring attitude is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers' classroom mentoring attitude is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers' classroom mentoring attitude is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the intellectual satisfaction of students adapted from Mayo (2016), which is divided into three domains, namely curiosity, engagement, and positive attitude. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach's alpha value of 0.918 interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability

and consistency among the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of intellectual satisfaction of students, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. In order to facilitate the gathering of the needed data, the researcher would first request ethical clearance from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee (REC) before she gathers data. After obtaining the ethical clearance from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee (REC), the

researcher sought endorsement from the office of the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, to conduct this study. The endorsement letter from the office of the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethical clearance from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee (REC) was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Su-

Range of Mean Descriptive Levels and Interpretations

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The intellectual satisfaction of students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The intellectual satisfaction of students is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The intellectual satisfaction of students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The intellectual satisfaction of students is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The intellectual satisfaction of students is never manifested.

pervisor, and the principals of the selected elementary public schools in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the approval to conduct the study, the researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the

researcher conducted the survey simultaneously. The respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent’s scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the classroom mentoring attitude and intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. It was also used to supply the answer for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (teachers’ classroom mentoring attitude) and dependent

(intellectual satisfaction of students) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by *r*. This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Linear Regression Analysis was applied to evaluate the significant influence of teachers’ classroom mentoring attitude on the intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao del Norte. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It was sequenced based on the study’s objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes and students’ intellectual satisfaction, the significant relationship between teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes and students’ intellectual satisfaction, and the

influence of teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes on students’ intellectual satisfaction.

Table 1 shows the summary of teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes of elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. As shown in the table, teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes obtained an overall mean score of 3.26, descriptively rated as moderately extensive, interpreted as sometimes observed. This implies that educators’ attitude, perspective, and methodology when offering guidance, assistance, and mentorship to their students in the classroom environment are occasionally witnessed. This is consistent with the argument presented by Mwangi and Otanga (2015) that maintaining a positive mentoring demeanor fosters a classroom ambiance marked by trust, reverence, and transparent communication. Consequently, students are inclined to participate actively and feel secure in expressing themselves, resulting in an environment conducive to learning.

Table 1. Summary of Teachers’ Classroom Mentoring Attitudes in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Emotional Support	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Administering Discipline	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Parents’ Coordination	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Academic Consultation	3.40	Extensive
Overall	3.26	Moderately Extensive

More so, teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of academic consultation acquired the highest mean score of 3.40, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of parents’ coordination acquired the highest mean score of 3.15 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. The result shows that teachers who adopt a mentoring attitude go beyond traditional instruction by providing individualized guidance tailored to each student’s unique needs and abilities. This personalized approach enables educators to recognize and address students’ diverse learning styles and challenges, thereby promoting academic success and engagement. This aligns with Ahmad and Zadh’a’s (2018) assertion that educators exhibiting a mentoring approach tend to offer academic direction,

personalized teaching, and avenues for students to seek assistance during difficult times.

The summary on the extent of intellectual satisfaction of students is shown in the Table 2. As shown in the table, the overall mean of intellectual satisfaction of students is 3.28 which is described as moderately extensive. It means that the intellectual satisfaction of students is sometimes manifested. This implies that the feeling of accomplishment, engagement, and alignment with one’s academic or intellectual goals and interests is sometimes manifested. This supports the idea of Gallo (2017) that when students experience intellectual satisfaction, they are more engaged in the learning process. They actively participate in class discussions, ask questions, and seek out additional information, leading to a more dynamic and interactive learning environment.

Table 2. Summary of Intellectual Satisfaction of Students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Curiosity	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Engagement	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Positive Attitudes	3.41	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

Moreover, intellectual satisfaction of students in terms of positive attitudes had the highest mean score of 3.41, described as extensive and interpreted as often manifested, while intellectual satisfaction of students in terms of curiosity, acquired the highest mean score of 3.18, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested. This means that when students feel intellectually fulfilled, they are more likely to approach learning with curiosity, enthusiasm, and a willingness to question and explore. This mindset encourages them to delve deeper into subjects, analyze complex issues, and seek out alternative perspectives, all of which are essential components of critical thinking. This aligns with Vidić's (2021) research indicating a strong correlation between intellectual fulfillment and the development of critical thinking abilities. Students who experience satisfaction in their intellectual pursuits are more predisposed to engaging in critical thinking, where they scrutinize information, evaluate evidence, and employ their knowledge to address intricate challenges. These competencies are vital for achieving success across diverse domains. Relationship Between Teachers' Classroom Mentoring Attitudes and Intellectual Sat-

isfaction of Students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

The results of the analysis of the relationship between teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes and students' intellectual satisfaction are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes have a significant positive, strong relationship with the intellectual satisfaction of students with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.626, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes changes, the intellectual satisfaction of students also changes significantly. The table also shows that teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of emotional support, administering discipline, parents' coordination, and academic consultation have a significant relationship with the intellectual satisfaction of students with a p-value of .000 which is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.668, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.491, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.725, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.883, p < 0.05$).

The result suggests that teachers who display enthusiasm for learning serve as positive role models for their students. By demonstrating a lifelong commitment to education and intellectual growth, they inspire students to adopt

a similar mindset and embrace learning as a rewarding and enriching experience. This aligns with Scribner's (2019) research indicating that educators who demonstrate curiosity and passion for their subject matter can ignite a sense

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between Teachers’ Classroom Mentoring Attitudes and Intellectual Satisfaction of Students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Emotional Support	0.668*	0.000	Reject H0
Administering Discipline	0.491*	0.001	Reject H0
Parents’ Coordination	0.725*	0.000	Reject H0
Academic Consultation	0.883*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Teachers’ Classroom Mentoring Attitudes	0.793*	0.000	Reject H0

**Significant @ p<0.05*

Legend: Perfect Correlation for r=1.00; Strong Correlation for 0.7r<1.00; Moderate Correlation for 0.3r<0.7; Weak Correlation for 0.3;r<0.00; No Correlation for r=0.00

of intellectual curiosity among students. When teachers convey enthusiasm and a genuine love for learning, it often encourages students to develop a similar attitude. This also aligns with Ruffalo’s (2017) perspective that educators who adopt a mentoring approach focused on creating a safe and welcoming classroom atmosphere can encourage students to feel at ease when posing questions, sharing ideas, and embracing intellectual challenges.

Influence of Teachers’ Classroom Mentoring Attitudes on the Intellectual Satisfaction of Students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

The significance of the influence of teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes on the intellectual satisfaction of students was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. Ta-

In addition, the table shows that there are domains of teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes that significantly influence the intellectual satisfaction of students. This table also indicates that teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of administering discipline

ble 4 shows that teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of emotional support, administering discipline, parents’ coordination, and academic consultation are considered predictors of the intellectual satisfaction of students; the model is significant, as evident in an F-value of 8.908 with p<0.05. It is therefore stated that teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes predict the intellectual satisfaction of students. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.692 indicates that teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes have contributed significantly to the variability of intellectual satisfaction of students by 69.20 from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 30.80 was credited to other factors not covered in this study.

and academic consultation are significant when considered predictors of the intellectual satisfaction of students. This means that the extent of intellectual satisfaction of students increases by 0.228 and 0.430 for each unit increase in teachers’ classroom mentoring attitudes. Thus,

Table 4. Significance on the Influence of Teachers' Classroom Mentoring Attitudes on the Intellectual Satisfaction of Students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte

Classroom Mentoring Attitudes	Estimates	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Emotional Support	-0.008	0.046	0.858	Accept H0
Administering Discipline	0.228**	0.053	0.000	Reject H0
Parents' Coordination	0.016	0.037	0.667	Accept H0
Academic Consultation	0.430**	0.035	0.000	Reject H0
R² = 0.692				
F-value = 106.161*				
p-value = 0.000				
<i>*Significant @ p<0.05</i>				

this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes significantly influence the intellectual satisfaction of students. One imperative concern of this undertaking is to find out whether the theories that serve as the framework of this study have been supported by the findings. As regards to Self-Determination Theory by Deci and Ryan (1985), teachers' mentoring attitude can significantly influence the intellec-

tual satisfaction of students by creating an environment that supports their psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness as outlined in Self-Determination Theory. By fostering autonomy, competence, and relatedness, teachers can empower students to become more self-directed, confident, and engaged learners, ultimately leading to greater intellectual satisfaction and academic success.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to determine which domains of teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes significantly influence the intellectual satisfaction of students utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a correlation technique. The researcher selected the 160 elementary school teachers in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, as the respondents through a random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure

high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, were rated as moderately extensive. In addition, teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of emotional support, administering discipline, and parents' coordination were also rated as moderately extensive, while teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of academic consultation were described as extensive. Intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, was rated as

moderately extensive. Moreover, intellectual satisfaction of students in terms of curiosity and engagement was also rated as moderately extensive, while intellectual satisfaction of students in terms of positive attitudes was rated as extensive. Teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes have a significant positive strong relationship with the intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte. In addition, teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of emotional support, administering discipline, parents' coordination, and academic consultation have a significant relationship with the intellectual satisfaction of students. Overall, teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes significantly influence students' intellectual satisfaction. Teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes regarding disciplining and academic consultation were found to be significant predictors of students' intellectual satisfaction.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: Teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, were rated as moderately extensive, indicating that the attitude, perspective, and methodology employed by educators when offering guidance, assistance, and mentorship to their students in the classroom environment is oftentimes observed. This bears similarity with Mwangi and Otanga's (2015) proposition that maintaining a positive mentoring demeanor fosters a classroom ambiance marked by trust, reverence, and transparent communication. Consequently, students are inclined to participate actively and feel secure in expressing themselves, resulting in an environment conducive to learning. Intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte was rated as moderately extensive denoting that the feeling of accomplishment, engagement, and alignment with one's academic or intellectual goals and interests is sometimes manifested. This aligns with Gallo's (2017) proposition that when students feel intellectu-

ally fulfilled, their engagement in the learning process increases. They demonstrate active involvement by participating in class discussions, posing inquiries, and pursuing supplementary knowledge, resulting in a more vibrant and participatory learning atmosphere. Teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes have a significant positive, strong relationship with the intellectual satisfaction of students in Dujali District, Davao Del Norte, suggesting that teachers who display enthusiasm for learning serve as positive role models for their students. This corresponds with Scribner's (2019) study, which suggests that instructors who exhibit curiosity and enthusiasm toward their subject matter can spark students' intellectual curiosity. When teachers express genuine passion and enthusiasm for learning, it frequently inspires students to adopt a similar mindset. Teachers' classroom mentoring attitudes in terms of administering discipline and academic consultation were significant predictors of students' intellectual satisfaction. This aligns with the principles of Self-Determination Theory as proposed by Deci and Ryan (1985), suggesting that teachers' mentoring demeanor plays a pivotal role in shaping students' intellectual satisfaction. By cultivating an environment that caters to students' psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, teachers can empower students to become more self-directed, confident, and engaged in their learning journey. This, in turn, leads to heightened intellectual satisfaction and academic achievement.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education may implement policies that prioritize teacher training and professional development programs focused on nurturing mentoring attitudes. Implementing policies that prioritize teacher training and professional development programs focused on nurturing mentoring attitudes is crucial for fostering a supportive and conducive learning environment. The Department of Education plays a pivotal role in

shaping the educational landscape and ensuring that teachers are equipped with the necessary skills and mindset to effectively mentor students. School heads may encourage a culture of mentorship within the school community by providing opportunities for teachers to mentor one another and collaborate on best practices. Encouraging a culture of mentorship within the school community is essential for fostering collaboration, professional growth, and ultimately, improving student outcomes. School heads play a crucial role in creating an environment where teachers feel supported and empowered to mentor one another. Teachers should continuously seek professional development opportunities to enhance mentoring skills and stay updated on best practices in mentorship. Continuous professional development is essential for teachers to stay abreast of current trends, research, and best practices in education, particularly in the realm of mentorship. By continuously seeking professional development opportunities, teachers can enhance their mentoring skills and remain effective mentors to their students. Students should advocate for supportive learning environments

where their intellectual needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are met. Students play a crucial role in shaping their learning environments, and advocating for supportive learning environments is essential for fostering their intellectual growth and satisfaction. By actively advocating for environments that meet their intellectual needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, students can contribute to creating a positive and conducive atmosphere for learning. Future researchers may explore the role of individual differences, such as cultural background and personality traits, in moderating the relationship between teachers' mentoring attitudes and student outcomes. Future researchers have the opportunity to delve deeper into understanding how individual differences, such as cultural background and personality traits, influence the relationship between teachers' mentoring attitudes and student outcomes. Exploring these factors can provide valuable insights into how mentoring practices can be tailored to meet the diverse needs of students and maximize their academic and personal development.

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